

Employee Motivation and Their Impact on Employee Performance in Banking Sector in Hyderabad Karnataka Region

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The process of motivation consists of three stages:-

1. A felt need or drive
2. A stimulus in which needs have to be aroused
3. When needs are satisfied, the satisfaction or accomplishment of goals.

A Manager feels challenge to Motivate the people in their respective job because this Motivation relates with that Internal forces which direct the people to act in a particular way to get something or satisfy their needs. A Manager has to make the people work as per the direction was given to him.

Motivated employees can lead to increased productivity and allow an organisation to achieve higher levels of output. Imagine having an employee who is not motivated at work. They will probably use the time at their desk surfing the internet for personal pleasure or even looking for another job. This is a waste of your time and resources.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To Understand the Present Scenario of Motivation Factors in Banking Sector.
- To Understand their Work Performance and Relation with the Motivation Factors
- To Know the extent up to which motivation has been able to meet employee prospect

ABSTRACT

Due to increased competition between Organization and their need to respond effectively to rapidly changing operational conditions, as well as to personnel requirements, has escalated the necessity to identify those factors that Improve Employee Performance.

For any organization to operate smoothly and without any interruption, employee cooperation cannot be replaced with anything else. It is of utmost importance that the employees of an organization not only have a good relationship with the top management, but also, they maintain a healthy and professional relationship with their coworkers.

The study focus on how motivational tools impact the performance of employee for betterment. A sample of individuals was selected and was interviewed with self-administrated questionnaire to obtain primary data. The results obtained indicate that if employees are positively motivated, it improves both their effectiveness and efficiency drastically for achieving organizational goals.

Keywords: Employee Motivation, Employee Performance, Productivity, Organizational Goals

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important functions of management is to create willingness amongst the employees to perform in the best of their abilities. Therefore the role of a leader is to arouse interest in performance of employees in their jobs.

III. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- The Scope of the Study is limited to the Banking Sectors in Hyderabad Karnataka Region Areas (Bellary, Bidar, Kalaburagi Yadgir, Raichur, and Koppal)
- This Study helps the Management to Know the Motivation Factors that Impact the Employees Performance.
- This Study also let us know the Satisfaction Level of the Employees

IV. METHODOLOGY ADOPTED

This study was undertaken in Banking Sectors of Hyderabad Karnataka Region (SBI, HDFC, IDBI, OBC, and UBI) to know Employee Motivation and their Impact on Employee Performance. Both Primary and Secondary data collection was made. Primary data is collected by structured survey. Secondary data is collected from different published sources like Report, Research papers, Websites etc. The Sample size was 200 respondents mainly Employees working in Banking Sectors of Hyderabad Karnataka Region.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

Smith and Rupp (2003) stated that performance is a role of individual motivation; organizational strategy, and structure and resistance to change, is an empirical role relating motivation in the organization.

Luthans and Stajkovic (1999) concluded that advancement of human resources through rewards, monetary incentives, and organizational behavior modification has generated a large volume of debate in the human resource and sales performance field.

Orpen (1997) better the relationship between mentors and mentees in the formal mentoring program, the more mentees are motivated to work hard and committed to their organization.

Vuori and Okkonen (2012) stated that motivation helps to share knowledge through an intra-organizational social media platform which can help the organization to reach its goals and objectives.

Den and Verburg (2004) found the impact of high performing work systems, also called human resource practices, on perceptual measures of firm performance.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Meaning -Motivation is the reason for people's actions, willingness and goals. Motivation is derived from the word motive in the English language which is defined as a need that requires satisfaction. These needs could also be wants or desires that are acquired through influence of culture, society, lifestyle, etc. or generally innate. Motivation is one's direction to behavior, or what causes a person to want to repeat a behavior, a set of force that acts behind the motives.

An individual's motivation may be inspired by others or events (extrinsic motivation) or it may come from within the individual (intrinsic motivation) Motivation has been considered as one of the most important reasons that inspires a person to move forward in life. Motivation results from the interaction of both conscious and unconscious factors.

Definition – Berelson and Steiner: “A motive is an inner state that energizes, activates, or moves and directs or channels behaviour goals.”

Lillis: “It is the stimulation of any emotion or desire operating upon one's will and promoting or driving it to action.”

Types of Motivation-

1. Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic motivation is a type of motivation in which an individual is being motivated by internal desires.

2. Extrinsic Motivation

Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is a type of motivation in which an individual is being motivated by external desires.

Minor Forms of Motivation

All types of motivation are going to fall into one of the two categories above. Now that we've covered these motivational types and provided you with some examples, here are minor forms of motivation that are capable of making a big impact in your life!

3. Reward-Based Motivation or Incentive Motivation

Incentive motivation or reward-based motivation is a type of motivation that is utilized when you or others know that they will be a reward once a certain goal is achieved.

Because there will be something to look forward to at the end of a task, people will often become more determined to see the task through so that they can receive whatever it is that has been promised.

The better the reward, the stronger the motivation will be!

4. Fear-Based Motivation

The word “fear” carries a heavy negative meaning but when it comes to motivation, this is not necessarily the case. Anyone who is big on goal-setting and achievement knows that accountability plays a huge role in following through on goals.

When you become accountable either to someone you care about or to the general public, you create a motivation for yourself that is rooted in the fear of failure. This fear helps you to carry out your vision so that you do not fail in front of those who are aware of your goal.

Fear-based motivation is extremely powerful as long as the fears are strong enough to prevent you from quitting.

5. Achievement-Based Motivation

Titles, positions, and roles throughout jobs and other areas of our lives are very important to us. Those who are constantly driven to acquire these positions and earn titles for themselves are typically dealing with achievement-based motivation.

Whereas those who use incentive motivation to focus on the rewards that come after a goal is met, those who use achievement-based motivation focus on reaching a goal for the sake of achievement.

Those who need a boost in their professional life will find achievement-based motivation extremely helpful.

6. Power-Based Motivation

Those who find happiness in becoming more powerful or creating massive change will definitely be fueled by power-based motivation.

Power-based motivation is a type of motivation that energizes others to seek more control, typically through the use of positions in employment or organizations.

Although it may seem to be a bad thing, power-based motivation is great for those who wish to change the world around them based on their personal vision.

7. Affiliation Motivation

Those who use affiliation motivation as a driving force to meet their goals thrive when they connect with others in higher power positions than them.

They also thrive when those people compliment the work that they do as well as their achievements.

Affiliation motivation is a great force to help you achieve your social goals and move up in the world.

8. Competence Motivation

Competence motivation is a type of motivation that helps others to push forward and become more competent in a certain area.

This type of motivation is especially helpful when it comes to learning new skills and figuring out ways around obstacles that one is faced with in different areas of life.

9. Attitude Motivation

Attitude motivation is a kind of motivation that comes to those who intensely desire to change the way that they see the world around them and the way that they see themselves. Goals associated with self-awareness and self-change will be met with attitude motivation.

Motivation is absolutely vital if you want to achieve your dreams. Using the 9 types of motivation mentioned above, nothing will be able to stand in the way of you and your goals any longer!

VI. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Good	180	90 %
Average	10	05 %
Poor	10	05 %
Total	200	100 %

Table 1: Are you satisfied with Salary Paid to you by the Banks

A. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Shows that 90% of the Employee said that they are satisfied with Salary being paid to them whereas 05 % said its Average and 05 % said its Poor. Salary is one of the Motivating Factors for the Employees Performance.

Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Good	160	80%
Average	20	10%
Poor	20	10%
Total	200	100 %

Table 2: Are you Satisfied with the Non Monetary Benefits paid to you (Health care benefits, Life Insurance, Promotion, Vehicle Allowance, Gift Cards, Vacation packages, Concert Tickets etc.,)

B. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 2 Shows that 80% of the Employee said that they are satisfied with Non Monetary Benefits being paid to them whereas 10 % said its Average and 10% said its Poor. Non Monetary Benefits Motivates an Employee to work more

Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	140	70 %
Average	50	25 %
Not Satisfied	10	05 %
Total	200	100 %

Table 3: Are you Satisfied with the Company Culture (Good Working Environment, Company Vision and Mission, Company Value, Company Ethics, Company expectations, and goals etc.,)

C. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 3 Shows that 70% of the Employee said that they are satisfied with Company Culture 25 % said its Average and 05 % said they are not satisfied. Company Culture Plays an Important role in Motivation of Employees. Many Companies Introduced Flexible Working hours to Motivate the Employees.

Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	160	80 %
Average	20	10 %
Not Satisfied	20	10 %
Total	200	100 %

Table 4: Are you Satisfied with the Learning and Development Opportunities Provided by the Company (Educating and guiding the employees on the areas and aspects that will help them develop and progress)

D. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 4 Shows that 80% of the Employee said that they are satisfied with Learning and Development Opportunities Provided by the Company 10 % said its Average and 10 % said they are not satisfied. Learning and Development Stimulates higher performance and improve engagement as long as the company offers development opportunities at every level - from learning on the job, through mentorship, shadowing and specific internal or external training programmes.

Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	180	90 %
Average	00	00 %
Not Satisfied	20	10 %
Total	200	100 %

Table 5: Are you Satisfied with the Recognition and Appreciation for the work done by you.

E. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 5 Shows that 90% of the Employee said that they are satisfied with the Recognition and Appreciation for the work done by them Whereas 10 % of them are not satisfied. Recognition and Appreciation also Motivates Employees.

Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	110	55 %
Average	80	40 %
Not Satisfied	10	05 %
Total	200	100 %

Table 6: Hows your Relationship with Superiors and Peers in dealing with Official Work (Delegation of Authority or Responsibility)

F. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 6 Shows that 55 % of the Employee said that they are satisfied with Relationship with Superiors and Peers in dealing with Official work 40 % said Average and 05 % said Not Satisfied. Cordial Relationship also plays an Important role in Motivation of an Employee.

Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	180	90 %
Average	10	05 %
Not Satisfied	10	05 %
Total	200	100 %

Table 7: Are you Satisfied with the Authority being given to you to complete the Task.

G. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 7 Shows that 90 % of the Employee said that they are Satisfied with the Authority being given to them to complete the Tasks 05 % said its Average and 05 % said they are not satisfied.

Particulars	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	150	75 %
Average	25	12.5 %
Not Satisfied	25	12.5 %
Total	200	100 %

Table 8: Are you Satisfied with the Growth Opportunity and Job Security Provided by the Banks.

H. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 8 Shows that 75 % of the Employee said that they are Satisfied with the Growth Opportunity and Job Security Provided by the Banks 12.5% said its Average and 12.5 % said Not Satisfied.

VII. CONCLUSION

From the data analysis presented above we can clearly come to the decision that the factors taken into account during the survey (Salary, Non Monetary Benefits, Company Culture, Learning and Development Opportunities, Recognition and Appreciation, Relationship with Superiors, Authority to take Decision, Growth Opportunity and Job Security.) Motivates an Employee to perform and achieve goals of the respective organization. Motivating an Employee is delicate and Challenging task that need to be reviewed on continuous basis.

Almost all the Employees are satisfied with the Salary and Non Monetary Benefits. The Working Culture is also Good in Banking Sectors. Also there is lot of Learning and Development Opportunities for the Employees for their Future Prospects. Staffs also get Recognition and Appreciation for their works. They also have Good

relationship with the Superiors and Peers which has to be improved further by Team Building Workshops. Employees are satisfied with the Growth Opportunity and Job Security given by the Banks.

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